

NOVEL FLEXIBLE BODY ARMOR UTILIZING SHEAR THICKENING FLUID (STF) COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The U.S. Army requires lightweight, flexible body armors that provide ballistic protection without significantly compromising soldier mobility and dexterity. Currently fielded systems employ multi-ply Kevlar[®] fabric armors, whose bulk and stiffness make them practical only for torso protection. To address this problem, we are investigating the ballistic properties of Kevlar fabrics impregnated with colloidal shear thickening fluids (STFs). STFs are fluids that undergo a sudden and dramatic increase in viscosity above a critical shear rate, in some cases transforming to a material that exhibits solid-like behavior. Impregnating Kevlar fabrics with this fluid results in a composite material which is flexible at low strain rates, such as during normal soldier motion, but stiffens upon sudden impact to provide ballistic protection. We have fabricated and tested a series of such materials. The shear thickening fluid is composed of silica particles with a nominal diameter of 446 nm at a loading of 57% v/v in ethylene glycol. Special fabrication techniques are used to ensure that the STF fully wets the Kevlar fabric (plain weave, 600 denier, KM-2). The results show that, under the conditions tested, the ballistic performance of the STF composite armors is equivalent to or slightly better than neat Kevlar armors of the same weight. However, the STF armors require significantly fewer layers of Kevlar fabric than the neat Kevlar armors. The resulting STF armors are therefore significantly more flexible, and thinner, than the conventional materials. Ballistic results for a range of STF composite architectures and materials will be presented and compared, and mechanisms for the enhanced ballistic performance will be proposed.

KEYWORDS: shear thickening fluid, body armor, composite, Kevlar, ballistic, flexible

INTRODUCTION

Military and law enforcement personnel require protective, conformal body armor to prevent injury or death from ballistic threats, including both gun-launched rounds and secondary fragments or shrapnel. State-of-the-art body armor materials include fabrics composed of high strength, high toughness fibers such as Kevlar[®], Zylon[®], or Tworon[®] fibers, and fiber-thermoplastic laminates such as Spectrashield[®] [1-4]. For high threat situations, rigid ceramic plates can also be incorporated to enhance ballistic protection.

These body armor materials have primarily been integrated into wearable vests, which offer only torso protection. However, injuries to the extremities, such as the arms, legs, and neck, can also prove incapacitating or fatal [5]. Current body armor materials have proven insufficient for providing protective systems for the extremities, due to their inflexibility and high bulk. To address this shortcoming, new materials are needed which offer comparable ballistic protection to existing materials, but with increased flexibility and less bulk.

Lee et al. [6, 7] have shown that a composite material composed of Kevlar fabric and shear-thickening fluid (STF) may offer a solution for extremities protection. STFs are fluids whose viscosity increases with shear rate [8-10]. Colloidal STFs are composed of a high concentration of rigid, sub-micron

particles stabilized in a carrier fluid. At low strain rates but beyond any yield stress, colloidal dispersions are fluid-like. For some dispersions at high strain rates, hydrodynamic forces overcome the interparticle stabilization forces, and the particles assemble into "hydroclusters" [11-16], which greatly increase the energy dissipation. As the strain rate increases further, the size and number of hydroclusters increases until the material macroscopically exhibits solid-like properties.

Colloidal STFs can be designed such that the shear-thickening transition is sharp, exhibiting liquid-like properties below a critical shear rate, and solid-like properties above this shear rate. The low strain rate viscosity, critical shear rate, and sharpness of the transition can be tailored through selection of particle size, shape, concentration, and surface properties, as well as carrier fluid properties [17, 18].

Lee et al. [6, 7] showed that STF-Kevlar composites could offer low-velocity ballistic performance comparable to neat Kevlar of similar areal density, but with much less bulk and higher flexibility. They also demonstrated that impregnation of the STF into the fabric is critical to achieving enhanced ballistic properties. In this paper we briefly review these earlier results, and provide additional ballistic results that suggest that the STF enhances ballistic protection through a modification to the yarn pull-out mechanism during impact.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The shear thickening fluids used in target fabrication and yarn pull-out tests were prepared through dispersing spherical silica particles (Nissan Chemicals MP4540, 446 nm silica particle diameter as determined by dynamic light scattering) in either ethylene glycol or polyethylene glycol ($M_n = 200$).

More recent experimental testing has been conducted on composite Kevlar fabric samples containing polyethylene glycol-based STFs, having lower volatility and demonstrating similar rheological performance when compared to ethylene glycol based STFs reported by Lee et al. [6, 7]. Rheological measurements of the experimental shear thickening fluids, having a particle volume fraction of approximately 0.57, demonstrate a reversible, shear thickening transition at shear rates between $10^2 - 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. A thorough account of the preparation and rheology of these shear thickening systems can be found in Lee et al. [6, 7] and Lee and Wagner [9].

Plain-woven Hexcel Aramid (poly-paraphenylene terephthalamide) high performance fabric (Style 706, Kevlar KM-2, 600 denier, areal density of 180 g/m^2) was used to fabricate ballistic targets and samples for fiber pullout investigations. The ballistic targets were prepared by impregnation of the shear thickening fluid. Both ethylene glycol and polyethylene glycol, having surface tension of 47.7 dyne/cm and 44.5 dynes/cm , respectively, were observed to wet the Kevlar fabric. To facilitate impregnation into the Kevlar fiber yarns through reduction of both STF surface tension and viscosity, an equal volume of ethanol was mixed with the glycol-based STFs prior to application. The composite fabric samples were then heated at 80°C for 20 minutes in a convection oven to remove all the ethanol. The efficacy of this technique for the impregnation of shear thickening fluids into the fabric structure on the filament level has been confirmed by earlier investigations [6, 7]. Scotch-Weld™ 2216 Epoxy Adhesive (3M Corporation) was used to fabricate rigid Kevlar fabric-epoxy resin composite targets.

Target assembly

An illustration of the target assembly is given in Fig. 1. Targets for ballistic testing were constructed with Kevlar fabric layers in $4.76 \text{ cm} \times 4.76 \text{ cm}$ sheets. All composite targets tested were encapsulated in 0.05 mm thick polyethylene film heat sealed at the edges to prevent fluid leakage. A piece of $5.08 \text{ cm} \times 5.08$

cm aluminum foil was placed on both sides of the target pouch and the assembly was secured by taping the edges.

To demonstrate the improvement in ballistic response resulting from impregnation with STF, targets composed of 4 Kevlar fabric layers were impregnated with different volumes of the ethylene glycol-based STF. For reference, targets were assembled containing 4, 10, 14 and 18 layers of neat Kevlar fabric. Targets with 4 Kevlar layers were fabricated with different amounts of ethylene glycol as a comparison to evaluate the effects of the carrier fluid. In addition, three targets were fabricated with 4 Kevlar layers and the dry colloidal silica particles from the shear thickening fluids. These dry silica target samples were prepared as before, using ethanol diluted, ethylene glycol-based shear thickening fluid. Following ethanol removal, the ethylene glycol was then removed by heating the composite targets at 100°C for 12 hours. To demonstrate the ballistic performance of a rigid Kevlar-epoxy resin composite, two 4 Kevlar fabric layer samples were fabricated through impregnation with Scotch-Weld™ 2216 epoxy resin followed by a 6 hour curing cycle at 80°C. The construction and properties of these targets are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Construction and properties of neat Kevlar and Kevlar composite targets.

Target description	Kevlar fabric layers	Material Impregnated	Impregnation pattern	Target areal density, (g/cm ²)
neat Kevlar	4	none	-	0.074
neat Kevlar	10	none	-	0.182
neat Kevlar	14	none	-	0.256
neat Kevlar	18	none	-	0.328
STF Kevlar	4	EG-based STF	full	0.186
STF Kevlar	4	EG-based STF	full	0.306
STF Kevlar	4	EG-based STF	full	0.539
silica Kevlar	4	dry silica	full	0.1891
silica Kevlar	4	dry silica	full	0.305
silica Kevlar	4	dry silica	full	0.539
epoxy Kevlar	4	epoxy resin	full	0.308
epoxy Kevlar	4	epoxy resin	full	0.541

Table 2 Construction and properties of full impregnated and patterned PEG based STF targets based on 6 layers of Kevlar.

Target description	Schematic of pattern	Target weight, (g)	Target areal density, (g/cm ²)
Fully-impregnated STF Kevlar		3.896	0.151
Fully-impregnated STF Kevlar		3.996	0.155
Center-impregnated STF Kevlar		3.048	0.118
Center-impregnated STF Kevlar		3.115	0.121
Edge-impregnated STF Kevlar		3.227	0.125
Edge-impregnated STF Kevlar		3.251	0.126
Stripe-impregnated STF Kevlar		3.086	0.120
Stripe-impregnated STF Kevlar		3.116	0.121
Stripe-impregnated STF Kevlar		3.141	0.122

In addition, nine targets containing 6 Kevlar fabric layers were constructed to evaluate the effectiveness of partial impregnation and impregnation patterning. Two targets were constructed of Kevlar fabric layers having only the centers of the fabric impregnated with polyethylene glycol-based STF. Two targets were constructed having only the edges impregnated with the STF. Three targets were constructed having shear thickening fluid placed in 6 equally spaced stripes on each of the fabric layers. In these stripe pattern targets, the Kevlar fabric layers were assembled to have alternating horizontal and vertical stripe orientations. For comparison, two completely impregnated targets with 6 Kevlar fabric layers targets were also tested. The construction and properties of the patterned STF composite targets are presented in Table 2.

To quantify ballistic performance, depth of penetration measurements were performed using 7.62 cm × 4.45 cm × 4.45 cm clay witnesses (Plastilina modeling clay, Van Aken International). Kevlar target backing supports were used between the target and the clay witness for all ballistic tests. These supports were fabricated using a single ply of neat Kevlar fabric glued to a 5.08 cm diameter copper hoop (0.635 cm wire diameter) using an adhesive (Liquid Nails, ICI) in order to help support the target during testing.

Ballistic Testing

Fig. 1 Ballistic test frame and target geometry.

Ballistic impact testing was performed on the targets using a smooth bore helium gas gun, and a NATO standard fragment simulation projectile (1.1 gram, chisel-pointed metal cylinder). All testing was performed at room temperature. The projectile velocity was adjusted to be approximately 244 m/s (800 ft/sec), and the projectile trajectory was adjusted to impact the center of the targets. The velocity of the projectile was measured using time-of-flight measurements between silverized witness papers immediately prior to target impact. An aluminum test fixture was fabricated for holding the target, support layer and clay witness during testing. The ballistic test set-up is illustrated in Fig. 1. The target was held in place during testing using metal clips.

The clay witness was calibrated to extract residual velocity of the projectile, V_r (m/s) from the depth of penetration L (m) as [6, 7]:

$$V_r = 38.9 + 3720L$$

The dissipated projectile kinetic energy is then calculated from an energy balance on the kinetic energy (assuming negligible heating):

$$E = \frac{1}{2} m_p (V_i^2 - V_r^2)$$

Where E is the dissipated energy (J), m_p is the projectile mass (kg), and V_i is the initial projectile velocity (m/s).

Pull-Out Testing

A possible mechanism for ballistic energy dissipation by Kevlar fabrics is frictional losses associated with yarn pull-out [19]. Yarn pull-out tests were performed on Kevlar fabric samples impregnated with STF to investigate the mechanisms by which shear thickening fluids assist in ballistic fabric energy dissipation.

Individual yarn pull-out testing was performed using an Instron model 4206 universal testing machine with a 1 kN load cell. A fabric tensioning fixture (Fig. 2) was fabricated using a published design [20]. Transverse loading of the fabric sample was applied with a calibrated spring.

Fig. 2 Yarn pull-out test fixture.

For pull-out testing, Kevlar test samples having a width of 25.4 cm and length of 19.05 cm were cut from Kevlar fabric. Approximately 120 of the transverse Kevlar yarns were removed from one end of the samples, allowing 8.89 cm of longitudinal fibers to remain free for longitudinal clamping in the universal test machine pneumatic grip. The remaining 10.16 cm of the sample length was clamped in place in the fixture. The transverse loading (perpendicular to the direction of pull-out) was adjusted to approximately 250 N. The distance between the clamped edges of fabric, measured as width, for all pull-out experiments was roughly 20.32 cm. During each of the pull-out tests, a single longitudinal Kevlar yarn located at the center of the fabric is clamped using the pneumatic grip, and is pulled from the transversely-loaded fabric at a crosshead speed of 50 mm/min. The universal test machine records the force vs. displacement for each of the experimental runs.

Pull-out testing was performed on four samples to evaluate the effects STF impregnation during yarn pull-out. Three samples were fabricated by impregnating a centrally located, horizontal stripe of shear thickening fluid having widths of approximately 5.1 mm, 10.2 mm and 20.3 mm into the Kevlar fabric samples, corresponding to a longitudinal coverage of 5%, 10% and 20%. The mass of polyethylene glycol-based STF per area of impregnated region following ethanol removal was approximately 0.009 g/cm² for all three samples. The fourth sample was fabricated from neat Kevlar fabric alone for comparison.

Fig. 3 Comparison of the ballistic performance of neat Kevlar, 4 layers of STF-impregnated Kevlar, 4 layers of dry silica-impregnated Kevlar, 4 layers of ethylene glycol-impregnated Kevlar, and 4 layers of epoxy resin-impregnated Kevlar.

Fig. 4 Effect of STF impregnation pattern on ballistic performance.

RESULTS

Ballistic Testing

Figure 3 compares ballistic performance of neat Kevlar with STF-Kevlar composites of similar areal density. On a per-weight basis, the two types of materials perform equivalently. However, the STF composite samples require significantly fewer layers of Kevlar than the equivalent neat Kevlar targets. This reduction in the number of layers of fabric leads directly to a decrease in the thickness of the target, and an increase in its flexibility. In fact, Lee et al. [6, 7] showed that the addition of STF to four layers of Kevlar resulted in no change in the flexibility of the Kevlar at low strain rates, and only a minor increase in its thickness. Maintaining flexibility upon impregnation with STF is expected because at low strain rates the STF behaves like a fluid and should not impede yarn or fabric mobility. The relatively small change in thickness with STF addition is due to the fact that the STF wets into the free space between fibers.

To demonstrate that the enhanced ballistic performance is caused by the shear-thickening effect, and not simply due to mass addition, Fig. 3 also compares the ballistic performance of Kevlar fabric impregnated with STF, unfilled ethylene glycol, dry silica powder, and a rigid epoxy. Note that the dry silica target was impregnated using methods very similar to the STF impregnation, so that we expect the silica to be intermingled with the fabric on a fiber level, rather than simply coating the yarns in the fabric. The comparison shows that the addition of neat ethylene glycol actually decreases the ballistic performance of the Kevlar fabric, probably due to lubrication effects. The addition of dry silica

provides a measurable enhancement to the Kevlar ballistic properties, but still performs less effectively than the STF-impregnated material. Finally, as shown in Fig. 3 a solid target composed of an epoxied Kevlar performs poorly in comparison to the pure Kevlar or the STF impregnated Kevlar until the target becomes massive enough to stop the projectile.

Figure 4 compares the ballistic performance of the patterned targets with the performance of neat Kevlar of similar areal density. Note that the patterning approach results in a lower mass target than the full impregnation approach. The energy absorption measurements do not show any significant differences in ballistic properties of the Kevlar patterned with a small amount of STF. However, patterning has a clear and dramatic effect on the fabric deformation and pull-out. Figure 5 shows the rear layer of Kevlar for each of these targets, and Fig. 6 shows a close-up of the edges of each of these layers. For the fully impregnated sample, there is little yarn pull-out evident. For the center-impregnated target, pull-out is observed at the edges of the sample. The fabric deformation at the center of the target is very blunt and distributed. In comparison, the edge-impregnated target exhibits little or no yarn pull-out, and a sharp fabric deformation at the center of the target. Presumably, there is significant inter-yarn relative motion at the target center. The stripe-impregnated targets show a deformation pattern that is perhaps intermediate between the center and edge deformation patterns. Interestingly, there was little clear evidence of a horizontal or vertical bias to the deformation patterns in each striped layer. Figure 7 compares the clay witness impact marks for the edge and striped impregnation patterns. Clearly the striped pattern resulted in a blunter, more evenly distributed deformation pattern, although the final depths of penetration for the two targets were very similar.

Fig. 5 Comparison of the last fabric layer for 6 layers of Kevlar with varying STF impregnation patterns.

Fig. 6 Close-up of the edge of the last fabric layer for 6 layers of Kevlar with varying STF impregnation patterns.

Fig. 7 Comparison of the impact marks left in the witness clay for 6 layers of Kevlar with (a) edge and (b) stripe impregnation patterns.

Pull-Out Testing

Figure 8 shows measurements of load versus displacement for yarn pull-out tests performed on the Kevlar fabric samples having varying amounts of impregnated STF. The curves are qualitatively similar, demonstrating a rapid increase in load until a displacement of approximately 8 mm is achieved. The initial loading increase corresponds to the straightening of the yarn in the fabric, which continues until this straightening propagates to the lower edge of the fabric. The second, decreasing load stage of the curve corresponds to bulk fiber translation through the fabric. The oscillations result as the yarn is pulled past each of the transverse yarns in the weave. It is evident from Fig. 8 that the addition of shear thickening fluid to fabric samples, even in small quantities, greatly increases the yarn pull out-load at constant crosshead speed.

Fig. 8 Yarn pull-out tests on Kevlar fabric samples having varying PEG-based STF areal coverage (10.16 cm sample length, 20.32 cm sample length, and transverse tension of 250 N).

to Kevlar fabric would reduce the cumulative yarn pull-out required to absorb a majority of the projectile's kinetic energy. This assertion is supported by the ballistic data, which shows that STF-impregnation reduces the number of Kevlar layers required to stop a projectile. By tailoring the pattern of STF impregnation, both within a single layer and from layer-to-layer, we hope to further improve ballistic efficiency through tailoring the location and extent of yarn pull-out. Although the present experiments only indicate a moderate performance enhancement through tailoring, the dramatic qualitative changes in fabric response suggest that significant performance gains could be possible through more intelligent patterning design.

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DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The ballistic results clearly demonstrate that the addition of STF to Kevlar fabric improves the ballistic properties of the fabric under fragment simulation projectile testing as compared to an equal number of layers of neat Kevlar. Further, comparisons to targets impregnated with the solvent, dry particles, and epoxied targets identifies the shear thickening response as the source of the added ballistic resistance. The localized nature of the yarn pull-out exhibited by the patterned targets suggests that the STF restricts the inter-yarn mobility by increasing the friction between yarns. This theory is supported by the static pull-out experiments, which demonstrate that the impregnation of STF dramatically increases the yarn pull-out energy. If these static experiments are a reasonable model of yarn pull-out at ballistic velocities, then we would expect that the addition of STF

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